

Title: Multiple Criteria Analysis for Ranking Alternatives

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Operational research is an applied science field that uses mathematical concepts to support decision-making. Multiple criteria analysis or multiple criteria decision methods (MCDM) are a class of techniques used to appropriately select alternatives based on multiple criteria or attributes that are often conflicting. MCDM methods are divided into Multi-Objective Decision Making (MODM) and Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM) [1,2]. The major difference of these families of methods is based on the determination of the alternatives (possible solutions). In former category, the alternatives are not predetermined but instead set of objective functions is optimized subject to a set of constraints. In the latter category, the alternatives are predetermined and a limited number of them is to be evaluated against a set of attributes [1].

MCDM domain offers methods for making choices that involve a complex interplay of factors, each with different levels of importance. Moreover, its techniques aim to provide a structured and systematic approach to such decision-making processes, offering a way to compare and rank alternatives. We scope to include MADM analysis in Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT) of XGAIN because the proposed technological solutions have to be assessed among different criteria, such as techno-economic, environmental and social and this process constitutes a formal and practical approach.

MADM methods are characterized as methods for dealing with a discrete set of alternatives with the goal of evaluating them via a list of criteria in order to rank them from best to worst, or just identify the best one. Some well-known and straightforward examples of MADM methods include TOPSIS [3] and VIKOR [4]. TOPSIS operates by identifying an optimal and an unfavorable solution, subsequently evaluating the proximity of each alternative to these two benchmarks. In contrast, VIKOR provides compromise solutions to problems that include non-commensurable and conflicting criteria. Both techniques rely on an amalgamating function that quantifies the proximity to the ideal scenario. As a result, TOPSIS and VIKOR have garnered significant interest within the academic community, prompting researchers to introduce numerous adaptations and extensions to these methodologies.

Indicatively, to clarify the process and gain the basic insight of the functionality in terms of multiple criteria analysis, we present the algorithmic steps that TOPSIS includes:

- Normalization of the decision matrix: All criteria are typically normalized to eliminate any scale effects and ensure that they can be meaningfully compared.
- Weight assignment: Decision-makers assign weights to each criterion to reflect their relative importance in the decision process. These weights can be based on subjective judgment or

calculated using various methods like the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) or the Analytic Network Process (ANP).

- Calculation of the ideal and negative ideal solutions: The ideal solution is obtained by maximizing each criterion (for benefit criteria) and minimizing each criterion (for cost criteria). The negative ideal solution is the reverse, minimizing benefits and maximizing costs.
- Calculation of the similarity score: Each alternative's similarity score is computed by evaluating its proximity to the ideal and negative ideal solutions using a distance metric, often the Euclidean distance or the Minkowski distance.
- Ranking alternatives: Alternatives are ranked based on their similarity scores. The one with the highest similarity score is considered the best choice.

The connection of aforementioned theory with the XGAIN is the necessity to provide ranking solutions to KFT users based on different criteria. Specifically, the KFT 'dimensioning solver' provides the mixture of connectivity (e.g. 5G or Wi-Fi) and processing enablers' (e.g. Raspberry Pi or NVIDIA Jetson Orin) technologies that are necessary to satisfy the requirements of users in rural areas. However, many different appropriate connectivity and computation configurations can be extracted by this module for the same users' demands. Each of these possible solutions (alternatives) have specific values in terms of the different criteria and the latter have different weights based on the preferences of users. Thus, all the possible solutions will be inserted in 'ranking' module and multiple criteria analysis will be applied to rank the solutions.

The multicriteria analysis is widely used in various fields, including engineering, economics, and environmental science and it provides a structured and logical approach to solving complex decision problems. These properties explain its inclusion in the proposed KFT architecture.

References

- [1] Ploskas, N., & Papathanasiou, J. (2019). A decision support system for multiple criteria alternative ranking using TOPSIS and VIKOR in fuzzy and nonfuzzy environments. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 377, 1-30.
- [2] Tzeng, G. H., & Huang, J. J. (2011). *Multiple attribute decision making: methods and applications*. CRC press.
- [3] Chakraborty, S. (2022). TOPSIS and Modified TOPSIS: A comparative analysis. *Decision Analytics Journal*, 2, 100021.
- [4] Opricovic, S., & Tzeng, G. H. (2007). Extended VIKOR method in comparison with outranking methods. *European journal of operational research*, 178(2), 514-529.

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